

LipAgg job announcement published

Deliverable number: D6.3

HORIZON EUROPE-MSCA-2024-Doctoral Network

LipAgg
DOCTORAL NETWORK
ON AMYLOID PROTEIN

**Funded by
the European Union**

Project Details	
Acronym:	LipAgg
Title:	From biophysical chemistry to cell biology: Deciphering the role of lipids in the toxicity and spreading of protein aggregation
Grant Number:	101227450
Call:	HORIZON-MSCA-2024-DN-01
Start date of the project:	01/03/2026
Project duration:	48 months

Deliverables Details	
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	Contributors	Institution	Status	Date
Deliverable leader:	Emilie Fontaine	CNRS	First version	05/05/2026
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Reviewers:	Lucie Khemtemourian	CNRS	Final version	28/05/2026

Disclaimer & acknowledgment

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1. Introduction to the LipAgg job announcement publication strategy

The LipAgg Doctoral Network aims to **recruit 15 highly qualified Doctoral Candidates (DCs)** to advance research on the role of lipids in protein aggregation, a key mechanism involved in neurodegenerative and metabolic diseases, including Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, and Type 2 Diabetes.

Deliverable D6.3, "Job Announcement Published", outlines **the strategy, implementation, and compliance of the recruitment and job advertisement process within the Horizon Europe MSCA Doctoral Networks** framework. It presents the publication and dissemination approach used for the PhD positions.

All 15 PhD positions were published in accordance with MSCA requirements, ensuring equal access and maximized international visibility. All job advertisements were systematically published on the LipAgg website.

The **EURAXESS portal was used as the mandatory publication platform**, as required under Horizon Europe MSCA rules. This was complemented by additional dissemination channels to maximize outreach and attract a diverse pool of highly qualified candidates from different academic and geographical backgrounds.

To further **enhance visibility and ensure broad dissemination**, the calls were also **distributed through multiple complementary channels**, including:

- National job portals
- The EURAXESS European research jobs portal
- LinkedIn professional networks

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2. Compliance of the LipAgg recruitment and selection process with MSCA requirements

The recruitment strategy implemented within the **Doctoral Network is fully aligned with the requirements of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA)** and the principles set out in the **European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct** for the Recruitment of Researchers. The overall process ensures full compliance with Horizon Europe MSCA Doctoral Networks standards.

In particular, the recruitment process is **open and publicly accessible**, as all vacancies were **advertised through widely visible channels**, ensuring that opportunities were available online to any eligible candidate. The dissemination strategy combined the **mandatory EURAXESS platform** with additional communication channels, including institutional websites, partner networks, and social media, in order **to maximise visibility and outreach at international level**.

The process is also **fully transparent**, as all recruitment activities explicitly reference the MSCA Doctoral Networks program and its rules, clearly outlining the framework, conditions, and commitments under Horizon Europe. This guarantees that candidates are fully informed of the program's requirements and recruitment standards.

As a result, the combination of open access, broad dissemination, and clearly procedures ensure that the recruitment process is **merit-based**.

Illustration of the LipAgg PhD position dissemination on **EURAXESS** (screenshots and excerpts).

The screenshot shows a job listing on the EURAXESS platform. At the top, it indicates 'JOB DENMARK EXPIRES SOON' and features the logos for the University of Copenhagen and the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions. The job title is 'Marie Curie PhD fellowship in stem cell biology at the Department of Drug Design and Pharmacology, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences'. The posting is from the University of Copenhagen, dated 1 May 2026. The description states: 'We are offering a Marie Curie PhD fellowship in stem cell biology commencing September 1st, 2026. Our group and research aims at understanding the role of dysfunctions in lipid homeostasis in the emergence of neurodegenerative diseases including Alzheimer's and Parkinson's Diseases. Our...'. Key details include: Department: Department of Drug Design and Pharmacology; Work Locations: Number of offers: 1, Denmark, Department of Drug Design and Pharmacology, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, 2100, Copenhagen, Universitetsparken 2; Research Field: Neurosciences, Chemistry » Biochemistry, Biological sciences; Researcher Profile: First Stage Researcher (R1); Funding Programme: Horizon Europe - MSCA; Application Deadline: 17 May 2026 - 23:59 (Europe/Copenhagen). A 'Share' button is visible at the bottom right.

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Job Information		Project description
Organisation/Company	University of Copenhagen	The selected PhD candidate will participate in the EU-funded HORIZON-MSCA-DN-2024-01 project LipAgg . The LipAgg network brings together partners from five European countries and comprises nine academic institutions and twelve industrial partners. The consortium is committed to delivering an outstanding training programme for fifteen doctoral candidates aimed at elucidating the role of lipids in the toxicity and propagation of protein aggregation.
Department	Department of Drug Design and Pharmacology	The Doctoral candidate key tasks will be to manage and carry out the assigned research project, participate in the LipAgg training and network activities, take PhD courses, write scientific articles and your PhD thesis, participate in national and international congresses and scientific meetings, undertake a research stay at an external research laboratory within the LipAgg network, and disseminate the obtained scientific results.
Research Field	Neurosciences Chemistry » Biochemistry Biological sciences	In particular, the doctoral candidate enrolled in this position, will investigate the cellular toxicity of amyloid-protein-lipid (AP-L) complexes in pancreatic cells and iPSC-derived neuronal cells. The cellular toxicity of the AP-L will be compared to that of lipid-free AP complexes. The influence of AP-L inhibitors on cell toxicity will also be investigated.
Researcher Profile	First Stage Researcher (R1)	The Doctoral Candidate will be enrolled at University of Copenhagen under the supervision of Associate Professor Céline Galvagnion. The project includes a 7-month secondment at Uppsala University under the supervision of Professor Anna Erlundsson, as well as a 1-month secondment in Lundbeck.
Positions	PhD Positions	The candidate The ideal candidate for this position is a highly motivated and talented researcher holding a master's degree (MSc or equivalent) in a field relevant to the position, e.g. stem cell biology, neuroscience, biochemistry. A solid background or keen interest in stem cell biology is highly desirable. The ideal candidate should be enthusiastic about tackling new scientific challenges and demonstrate strong motivation, persistence, and a results-oriented mindset. The candidate should be able to work effectively both independently and as part of an interdisciplinary team.
Application Deadline	17 May 2026 - 23:59 (Europe/Copenhagen)	Excellent oral and written communication skills in English are essential. Strong organisational and planning abilities are also required.
Country	Denmark	This position is subject to the mobility and eligibility rules of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions. In particular, the candidate must not have resided or carried out their main activity (work, studies, etc.) in Denmark for more than twelve months during the three years immediately prior to the recruitment date, unless as part of a procedure for obtaining refugee status under the Geneva Convention. At the date of recruitment, the candidate must be a Doctoral Candidate, i.e. in the first five years (full-time equivalent research experience) of their research career and must not have been awarded a doctoral degree.
Type of Contract	Temporary	Principal supervisor is Associate Professor Céline Galvagnion, Department of Drug Design and Pharmacology, E-mail: celine.galvagnion@sund.ku.dk ; Tel: +45 3533 7828.
Job Status	Full-time	Start: September 1st, 2026
Hours Per Week	37	Duration: 3 years as a PhD student
Offer Starting Date	1 Sep 2026	
Is the job funded through the EU Research Framework Programme?	Horizon Europe - MSCA	
Is the Job related to staff position within a Research Infrastructure?	No	

Eligibility

Applicants will also be required to meet the European Commission's MSCA Doctoral Network eligibility criteria, notably:

- Mobility Rule - Applicants can be of any nationality and must not have resided or carried out their main activity (work, studies, etc.) in Denmark for more than 12 months in the 36 months immediately before the start of their employment at UCPH. Compulsory national service, short stays such as holidays, and time spent as part of a procedure for obtaining refugee status under the Geneva Convention are not considered.
- Doctoral Candidate requirement – the applicant must not be in possession of a doctoral degree at the first day of the employment. Researchers who have successfully defended their doctoral thesis, but who have not yet been awarded the doctoral degree are not eligible.
- Doctoral Candidate requirement – the applicant must be –at the date of recruitment – formally admitted to a PhD programme leading to the award of a degree in at least one EU Member State or Horizon Europe associated country. For that purpose, candidates must meet the national requirements for doctoral enrolment in the host country. Proof of admission must be provided prior to the start of the contract.
- Be working exclusively for the action.

Eligibility conditions were mentioned in each publication.

In accordance with MSCA rules, applicants were required **not to hold a doctoral degree at the date of recruitment** and could be of any nationality. Furthermore, all candidates had to comply with the MSCA **mobility rule**, meaning they must not have resided or carried out their main activity (work, studies, etc.) in the country of the recruiting organization for more than 12 months during the 36 months immediately preceding the recruitment date.

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3. Standardized publication of LipAgg PhD job advertisements across the LipAgg consortium

The vacancy notices were prepared using a harmonized template to ensure consistency, transparency, and equal access to information across all 15 positions. Each announcement provided the same level of detail, thereby supporting a merit-based selection process.

Below is the structure and information included in the common LipAgg job description template:

- **Description of the LipAgg project and program**, including:
 - the LipAgg Doctoral Network Program
 - the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Grant Agreement number
 - a link to the project website
- **Description of the individual research project**
 - identification of the supervisor (i.e. Principal Investigator) and co-supervisor
 - information on both academic and non-academic secondments
- **Eligibility criteria**, including:
 - academic degree requirements (i.e. candidates who must not already hold a doctoral degree at the date of recruitment)
 - MSCA mobility rule
 - language and communication skills
- **Funding information**, including a clear description of the MSCA funding scheme (living allowance and mobility allowance). Based on the information provided by the different local institutions, the closest estimate to the gross salary was indicated.
- **Required application documents**
- **Recruitment date** (1 September 2026)
- **Contact information** for the supervisor and co-supervisor
- **Recent representative publications** of the supervisor and co-supervisor

To ensure consistency and fairness across the consortium, a **harmonized application procedure was adopted for all positions**. Candidates were required to submit **the same set of application documents** regardless of the recruiting institution, although the submission method could vary depending on local institutional procedures (email or application form).

Required application documents :

- CV, including methodological skills
- Motivation letter
- Copy of Master's degree (or proof of expected completion)
- Master's thesis (if available)
- Full academic transcripts
- Contact details of at least two referees

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4. Role of the LipAgg website in the publication and visibility of job offers

The LipAgg website was used as a **central communication and reference platform** for the Doctoral Network. The website served as the main hub for presenting the project and redirecting candidates to the relevant application channels.

The main objective of this approach was to **centralize all key information in a single accessible platform, facilitating candidate understanding of the LipAgg Doctoral Network** as an integrated and coherent research program, rather than a collection of independent PhD positions. Also, the strategy of redirection link to apply, was chosen to ensure the simplest possible application process for candidates and to avoid duplicate applications. In some cases, local internal procedures required candidates to apply through the university website in order to complete the application form.

LipAgg project page « Apply now » :

The screenshot shows the LipAgg website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links: HOME, PROJECTS (with a sub-link 'Apply Now'), TEAM, PARTNERS, and NEWS & EVENTS. Below the navigation bar, a teal banner reads: "We are excited to announce the recruitment of 15 PhD students to join the LipAgg European Doctoral Network !".

The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column, titled "LipAgg Doctoral Network projects", lists project details:

- Living abroad
- 2 academic partners
- 1 non-academic partner
- Training workshops around Europe
- Interdisciplinary Network

Doctoral Candidate Projects:
Browse a brief description of each project below. For full details and to apply, visit the host institution's website. You may select and apply to 1 or more doctoral positions.

Eligibility and Requirements:

- Doctoral candidates must not have a doctoral degree at the date of their recruitment.
- Doctoral candidates can be of any nationality.
- Doctoral candidates should comply with the "mobility rule": in general, they must not have resided or carried out their main activity (work, studies, etc.) in the country of the recruiting organisation for more than 12 months in the 36 months immediately before their recruitment date.

The right column, titled "DC7 project:", features an "Apply now" button. The text describes the project: "The Doctoral Candidate (DC) enrolled in this position, will identify mechanisms by which astrocytes spread Amyloid Protein-Lipid (AP-L) complexes and study if the AP-Ls induce astrocytic stress responses that affect their interplay with neurons. The candidate will expose cultures of human iPCS-derived astrocytes to fluorescently labelled AP-L complexes and analyze how the cells accumulate and spread the complexes over time using live cell imaging, immunocytochemistry, ELISA, Western blot, electron microscopy and other techniques. Moreover, the DC will isolate deposits of amyloid complexes from human astrocytes and determination of their lipid composition. Moreover, the DC will isolate deposits of amyloid complexes from human astrocytes for DC10."

Below the text, it lists "2 Host institutions:" with logos for UPPSALA UNIVERSITET (Host institution) and CNRS (Secondment institution). It also lists an "Associate partner: Bioartic" and a "Partner: BIOARTIC".

At the bottom of the right column, it lists the "Host PI: Supervisor: Anna Erlundsson – Professor, Department of Public Health and Caring Sciences; Molecular Geriatrics / Rudbeck Laboratory, Sweden" and the "Co-supervisor: Lucile Khemtemourain – Research Director, Laboratory of Chemistry and Biology of Membranes and Nano-objects, Spectroscopy and Imaging of Membrane-Active Peptides Team, CNRS / Bordeaux INP / University of Bordeaux, France".

At the bottom left of the screenshot, there is a link: "List of offered PhD projects for doctoral candidates (DC)".

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5. Dissemination and publication strategy for PhD recruitment calls

The dissemination strategy for the PhD vacancies was implemented as an **open, inclusive and internationally oriented recruitment process**. Its main objectives were to attract high-level international candidates, ensure a broad diversity of academic and geographical profiles, and comply fully with MSCA principles.

A **coordinated communication strategy was implemented via the LipAgg LinkedIn page**, which served as a central dissemination hub for the 15 PhD positions. However, due to local internal organization constraints (institutional procedures, internal validation processes, and publication rules varying between universities), not all vacancies could be published simultaneously on the national university websites and associated EURAXESS platforms.

The publication of all 15 PhD positions took place mainly between April and mid-May.

All PhD advertisements were published on LipAgg website and were disseminated through multiple complementary channels in order to maximize visibility (national job portal, EURAXESS European research jobs portal, LinkedIn networks).

This dissemination strategy aimed to actively **involve all members of the consortium**, including beneficiaries as well as academic and non-academic partners. **By engaging the full network, the approach maximized visibility through “ripple effects” across each partner’s communication channels, while also fostering a strong sense of unity and cohesion within the consortium.**

Screenshot of a PhD position on a university website:

universit PARIS-SACLAY

Retour

DESIGN AND SYNTHESIS OF INHIBITORS OF A-SYNUCLEIN AGGREGATION AND A-SYNUCLEIN-LIPID INTERACTION

INFORMATIONS CLÉS

Etablissement: Universit Paris-Saclay GS Sant et mdicaments

cole doctorale: [Innovation thrapeutique : du fondamental  l'appliqu](#) [i](#) Modalits de candidature

Spcialit: Chimie mdicinale

Unit de recherche: [Biomolcules : conception, isolement, synthse](#)

Encadrement de la thse: [Sandrine ONGERI](#)

Financement: du 01-09-2026 au 31-08-2029 Origine des fonds: MSCA- Marie Curie Grant Agreement Number 101227450
Employeur: Universit Paris-Saclay
Europe - MSCA (Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action)

The successful candidates will receive a gross salary of 3298 euros per month for the living allowance and of 710 euros per month for the Mobility (and a family allowance, if applicable) in accordance with the MSCA regulations for Doctoral Researchers. The PhD funding is for 36 months.

Dbut de la thse le: 1er septembre 2026

Date limite de candidature ( 23h59): 6 mai 2026

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Screenshot of dedicated announcements posts published by LipAgg:

LipAgg MSCA DN
224 abonnés
2 sem. •

🚀 Ready to take your PhD to the next level?
We are recruiting 15 Doctoral Candidates!

Join LipAgg and become part of an international, interdisciplinary, and inter-sectoral Doctoral Network offering 15 PhD positions across diverse scientific fields (biophysics, molecular biology, biochemistry, and computational biochemistry).

This is more than a PhD — it's an opportunity to:

- 🌟 be trained as a highly skilled doctoral candidate
- 🌟 stimulate your creativity
- 🌟 enhance your innovation capacities
- 🌟 boost your employability in the long-term

By joining LipAgg, you will collaborate with leading researchers and connect with peers across Europe, building relationships that will shape your future career. We are ready to welcome 15 motivated doctoral candidates for an intellectually stimulating and deeply human journey.

👉 Discover all positions and apply now: <https://lipagg.eu/>

Anna ErlandssonCeline GalvagnionLucie KhemtemourianCarmelo La RosaBirgit StrodelGunnar Schrödersandrine ongeriRita Guzzi @Christian Griesinger

#PhD #Hiring #ResearchJobs #HorizonEurope #MSCA #DoctoralNetwork #Biophysics #Biochemistry #MolecularBiology #ComputationalBiochemistry #Europe #LipAgg

Afficher la traduction

LipAgg - European Doctoral Network : amyloid protein-lipid
lipagg.eu

👍 Vous et 19 autres personnes 7 replications

🔥 15 PhD Positions Available Across Europe | Join the LipAgg Doctoral Network 🔥

Are you a scientist trained in biophysics, molecular biology, biochemistry, or computational biochemistry, ready to tackle some of the biggest molecular challenges behind major diseases?

- 🔴 Alzheimer's
- 🔴 Parkinson's
- 🔴 Type 2 Diabetes

We are recruiting 15 Doctoral Candidates for the EU-funded LipAgg MSCA Doctoral Network — a unique opportunity to explore how amyloid-lipid aggregates drive disease mechanisms.

🎯 The Mission
Understand how harmful protein-lipid complexes:

- Form and evolve
- Damage cell membranes
- Spread between cells

🌍 A Truly European Experience
Join a vibrant consortium of 23 academic & industrial partners across 6 countries. Work in an interdisciplinary, international, and collaborative environment at the forefront of science.

🎁 What You'll Gain

- Interdisciplinary, hands-on training with state-of-the-art technologies
- Exposure to both academia and industry
- European mobility & secondments
- A strong foundation for a high-impact research career

🌐 Find more details and apply now on www.lipagg.eu
A few final touches are currently being made on LipAgg website.

Anna Erlandsson Celine Galvagnion Lucie Khemtemourian Carmelo La Rosa Rita Guzzi Birgit Strodel Gunnar Schröder sandrine ongeri @Christian Griesinger

#PhD #Hiring #MSCA #HorizonEurope #Biophysics #Biochemistry #MolecularBiology #ResearchJobs #Europe #LipAgg #DoctoralNetwork

Posts were tailored for social media formats, particularly LinkedIn, with concise and structured messaging, and systematically included a direct link to the LipAgg website to guide candidates towards full project information and application details.

All supervisors were systematically included to strengthen visibility and ensure proper representation of the consortium.

The dissemination strategy included the use of targeted hashtags designed to highlight key aspects of the recruitment process, such as the open PhD positions, European funding support, and the specific scientific field of the LipAgg Doctoral Network.

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Example extracts of reposts, comments, and likes from consortium members (supervisors, universities) to amplify visibility of the 15 PhD positions:

12 reposts

Département Sciences et Technologies pour la Santé reposted this

LipAgg MSCA DN
4w • Edited •

15 PhD Positions Available Across Europe | Join the LipAgg Doctoral Network

... more

LipAgg - European Doctoral Network : amyloid protein-lipid
lipagg.eu

Cecile F.E. Bacles PhD and 28 others 3 comments • 12 reposts

Like Comment

sandrine ongeri reposted this

LipAgg MSCA DN
4w • Edited •

15 PhD Positions Available Across Europe | Join the LipAgg Doctoral Network

... more

LipAgg - European Doctoral Network : amyloid protein-lipid
lipagg.eu

Cecile F.E. Bacles PhD and 28 others 3 comments • 12 reposts

Like Comment

A Truly European Experience
Join a vibrant consortium of 23 academic & industrial partners across 6 countries. Work in an interdisciplinary, international, and collaborative environment at the forefront of science.

What You'll Gain

- Interdisciplinary, hands-on training with state-of-the-art technologies
- Exposure to both academia and industry
- European mobility & secondments
- A strong foundation for a high-impact research career

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A few final touches are currently being made on LipAgg website.

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#PhD #Hiring #MSCA #HorizonEurope #Biophysics #Biochemistry #MolecularBiology #ResearchJobs #Europe #LipAgg #DoctoralNetwork

LipAgg - European Doctoral Network : amyloid protein-lipid
lipagg.eu

Cecile F.E. Bacles PhD and 28 others 3 comments • 12 reposts

Like Comment Repost Send

Add a comment...

Most relevant

Max Planck Institute for Multidisciplinary Sciences
79,654 followers

You can join the consortium in our department of NMR-based Structural Biology! 🍷 We offer two PhD positions in the LipAgg Network, applications open until May 17th: <https://www.mpinat.mpg.de/626404/jobs>

4

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Illustration of individual posts by principal investigator highlighting their doctoral candidates (as supervisors or co-supervisor) to reach a wide audience :

Birgit Strodel • 1er
Group leader at Research Centre Jülich & Associate Professor at University ...
1 mois • 🔒

Are you a Biophysicist, Physical Chemist, or Biochemist ready to build "Digital Twins" of amyloid-lipid systems?

We are seeking a highly motivated Doctoral Candidate to join the EU-funded LipAgg MSCA Doctoral Network for a unique project bridging AI-augmented simulations and experimental spectroscopy.

This PhD position offers an incredible interdisciplinary journey across three different European institutions!

The Project:
Modeling (Jülich, Germany): Develop digital twins of amyloid-lipid complexes using high-performance simulations and enhanced sampling at @Forschungszentrum Jülich.
AI & Machine Learning (Nuth, The Netherlands): A 3-month secondment at @Aminoverse to apply AI methods to protein modeling.
EPR Spectroscopy (Italy): A 6-month secondment at @Università della Calabria with Prof. Rita Guzzi, performing hands-on Electron Paramagnetic Resonance experiments to validate your models.

Professional Development: Supervised by Prof. Birgit Strodel, you will be enrolled at @Heinrich-Heine-Universität Düsseldorf. This PhD project provides a comprehensive toolkit in computational biophysics, AI, and experimental physics—ideal for a high-level career in biomolecular research.

Who are we looking for?
An MSc in Biophysics, Biochemistry, Physical Chemistry, or a related field.
A strong foundation in molecular simulations.
A passion for both coding/AI and hands-on experimental work (EPR).
A researcher eager to collaborate across a diverse European network.

Why join LipAgg? Join a prestigious consortium of 11 academic and 12 industrial partners across 6 countries. We are committed to an inclusive working environment where everyone can realize their potential.

How to apply: Full details and eligibility: <https://lnkd.in/dSihx3Cg>
Application deadline on 07 May 2026.
Project website: www.lipagg.eu

#PhD #Biophysics #Hiring #MSCA #HorizonEurope #AI #MolecularDynamics #EPR #Spectroscopy #Jülich #LipAgg #PhysicsJobs

Lucie Khemtemourian • 1er
Researcher at Centre national de la recherche scientifique
3 sem. • 🔒

🔗 PhD Opportunities | Doctoral Candidate – LipAgg Doctoral Network 🌟

Would you like to pursue a PhD within a high-impact project like LipAgg, with secondments in prestigious academic institutions and non-academic partners, while benefiting from a European network, international training, and a strong scientific community?

👉 We are recruiting!

As Supervisor of DC5 and Co-supervisor of DC3, DC6, and DC7, I'm truly excited to connect with and recruit the next generation of PhD researchers who will shape the future of LipAgg 🌟

Doctoral Candidates are hosted across top institutions in France, Germany, Sweden, and Italy — join us and be part of a truly international scientific adventure! 🌍🔗

📍 DC5 – CNRS Bordeaux | Structural characterization of lipid-associated IAPP and Aβ fibrils in Type 2 Diabetes and Alzheimer's disease
📍 Secondments: Forschungszentrum Jülich | Non-academic – Research Pieces

📍 DC3 – University of Catania | Biophysical characterization of IAPP–lipid complexes in Type 2 Diabetes
📍 Secondments: CNRS | Non-academic – Biofordrug

📍 DC6 – Max Planck Institute | NMR structure of AP-L complex of hIAPP and its effects on fibrils and membranes
📍 Secondments: CNRS | Non-academic – Bruker

📍 DC7 – Uppsala University | Effects of Amyloid Protein–Lipid (AP-L) complexes on astrocyte–neuronal interplay and cell-to-cell propagation
📍 Secondments: CNRS | Non-academic – BioArctic

📅 Start date: 1 September 2026 | 🏆 36-month funding

📄 Applications are open now

👉 Please visit our website to find more information and apply: www.lipagg.eu

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Evidence of additional publications mentioning the recruitment by partners on their own LinkedIn accounts or institutional websites to strengthen the consortium's ties :

PhD in computational science with an industrial perspective

What if your research contributes to molecular understanding and pushes the scientific boundaries beyond established fields? At Aminoverse, we support young talent and advance cutting-edge science, including projects beyond enzyme discovery and engineering.

LipAgg MSCA DN investigates how amyloid protein–lipid aggregates drive processes such as aggregation, cellular toxicity, and intercellular spread. Focusing on proteins such as amylin, amyloid- β , and α -synuclein, the project explores the lipid-chaperone hypothesis and the role of protein–lipid complexes in membrane damage.

Aminoverse supports one of the 15 PhD projects through a 3-month industrial secondment, contributing expertise in computational modelling and biophysical simulations.

This project focuses on:

- Interaction of amyloid protein–lipid complex interactions with membranes
- Employment of enhanced molecular simulation techniques
- Integration of experimental EPR spectroscopy data

Our collaboration provides a unique platform where computational methodologies are converted into actionable insights within an applied biotech framework, effectively bridging the gap between fundamental academic research and industrial application.

If your interest lies in computational science and you want to change medicine by unveiling the interactions of amyloid protein-lipid complexes, we encourage you to apply here: <https://lipagg.eu/>

[#ComputationalScience](#) [#Biophysics](#) [#PhD](#) [#MSCA](#) [#Secondment](#)

MAX PLANCK INSTITUTE FOR MULTIDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES

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EU funds interdisciplinary doctoral network LipAgg

Early-career researchers can apply for 15 open positions across Europe (France, Germany, Italy, Denmark, Sweden)

MAY 08, 2026

LipAgg
DOCTORAL NETWORK ON AMYLOID PROTEIN

Contact
Prof. Dr. Christian Griesinger
Director
T: +49 531 201-2200
E: cgr@...
Department of NMR-based Structural Biology

Further information
To the 15 open positions
Website of the LipAgg- Network

In a nutshell

- **New PhD network LipAgg:** The EU is funding the Doctoral Network as part of the "Horizon Europe Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions" program.
- **MPI participation:** Christian Griesinger of the Max Planck Institute for Multidisciplinary Sciences (MPI-NAT) is one of nine principal investigators participating in the network.
- **15 PhD positions:** All positions are available on the LipAgg website. The application deadline for the two PhD projects advertised at the MPI-NAT is May 17, 2026.

Disclaimer & acknowledgment

Horizon Europe / Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions (MSCA) / Doctoral Network / LipAgg Grant agreement ID: 101227450

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Each consortium partner disseminated the PhD vacancy information on relevant national platforms, according to their own channels, in order to increase the visibility of the LipAgg project.

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15 PhD Positions Available Across Europe

🔥 15 PhD Positions Available Across Europe | Join the LipAgg Doctoral Network 🔥

Are you a scientist trained in biophysics, molecular biology, biochemistry, or computational biochemistry, ready to tackle some of the biggest molecular challenges behind major diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases and type 2 diabetes?

We are recruiting 15 Doctoral Candidates for the EU-funded LipAgg MSCA Doctoral Network — a unique opportunity to explore how amyloid-lipid aggregates drive disease mechanisms.

The Mission
Understand how harmful protein-lipid complexes:

- Form and evolve
- Damage cell membranes
- Spread between cells

A Truly European Experience
Join a vibrant consortium of 23 academic & industrial partners across 6 countries. Work in an interdisciplinary, international, and collaborative environment at the forefront of science.

What You'll Gain

- Interdisciplinary, hands-on training with state-of-the-art technologies
- Exposure to both academia and industry
- European mobility & secondments
- A strong foundation for a high-impact research career

Special note for NMR and Cryo-EM enthusiasts:
Out of the 15 positions, 3 PhD projects will focus on NMR and 2 on Cryo-EM, providing targeted opportunities for researchers interested in these techniques.

🌐 Find more details and apply now on [<http://www.lipagg.eu/> | www.lipagg.eu]

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PhD Student Structural Characterisation Of α -Synuclein-Lipid Complexes

The LipAgg project seeks to unravel the structural complexities of amyloid protein-lipid aggregates and investigate their role in pathological aggregation, cellular toxicity, and intercellular spread. Focusing on key human amyloid proteins—amylin (IAPP), amyloid beta (A β), and α -synuclein (α S)—linked to type 2 diabetes (T2D), Alzheimer's disease (AD), and Parkinson's disease (PD), respectively, the project builds on recent discoveries made by the consortium. These findings highlight the critical role of free lipids in membrane damage through the formation of stable lipid-amyloidogenic protein complexes, leading to the lipid-chaperone hypothesis.

The selected PhD candidate will participate in the EU-funded HORIZON-MSCA-DN-2024-01 project LipAgg. The LipAgg network brings together partners from 6 European countries and comprises 11 academic or research institutions and 12 industrial partners. The consortium is committed to delivering an outstanding training programme for 15 Doctoral Candidates (DCs) aimed at elucidating the role of lipids in the toxicity and propagation of protein aggregation.

This project aims at establishing a reproducible protocol to generate α -Synuclein-lipid complexes made from recombinant α -Synuclein and near physiological vesicle preparations, the characterisation of their stability using FIDA/Prometheus and their structure at the near atomic resolution using solid state NMR.

The Doctoral candidate key tasks will be to manage and carry out the assigned research project, participate in the LipAgg training and network activities, take PhD courses, write scientific articles and the PhD thesis, participate in national and international congresses and scientific meetings, undertake a research stay at an external research laboratory within the LipAgg network, and disseminate the obtained scientific results.

In particular, the DC enrolled in this position, will determine the structure of such α -Synuclein-lipid complexes by NMR spectroscopy in combination with photo-bleaching for the determination of the stoichiometry of the complexes and standard models. The project is expected to provide a high-impact research contribution.

Posted on 16 April 2026

Location:
Denmark

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<https://LipAgg.eu/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/LipAgg/>

zenodo

LipAgg

HORIZON EUROPE-MSCA-2024-Doctoral Network

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